

Zinc sensor

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Abstract : Zinc is available in highest amount in human body and is the constituent of more than 300 metalloenzymes. Zinc imbalance in body causes many life threatening problems. Different analytical techniques are used to quantitatively identify zinc concentration; however, fluorescence spectroscopy is more versatile and useful. We have designed a vanillinyl Schiff base which shows unprecedented fluorescent zinc sensing. Zinc induced turn-on fluorescence enhancement is observed at 472 nm. Formation of the 1 : 1 metal-to-ligand complex has been ascertained by Job's plot. Limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest, 0.018 μM in the family of fluorogenic Zn^{2+} -sensors.

Introduction

Zinc (Zn, 30, $[\text{Ar}]3d^{10}4s^2$) belongs to Group 12 along with cadmium (Cd) and mercury (Hg) (previously Gr. IIB) in the Modern Periodic Table¹. Earth's crust contains $\sim 0.0075\%$ Zn, making it the 24th most abundant element. Soil contains 5–770 ppm of zinc with an average of 64 ppm. Zinc occurs widely in different minerals namely, sphalerite (ZnFe)S; World production of Zinc is about 7 million tons p.a. and major producers are Canada (1 million ton), Australia (1 million ton), China (0.8 million tons) p.a.

Zinc is the most important trace metal in biology. Zinc requires for the body's defensive (immune) system². It appears in highest concentration in the human body. It plays a role in cell division, cell growth, wound healing, and the breakdown of carbohydrates. Zinc is also needed for the senses of smell and taste; it regulates gene expression, apoptosis, neural signal transmitters. During pregnancy, infancy, and childhood the body needs zinc to grow and develop properly. High-protein foods contain high amounts of zinc. Beef, pork, and lamb contain more zinc than fish. Other good sources of zinc are nuts, whole grains, legumes, and yeast. Zinc is in most multivitamin and mineral supplements. These supplements may contain

zinc gluconate, zinc sulfate, or zinc acetate. More than 300 metallo-enzymes are either directly or indirectly related with Zinc²⁻⁴. It does not provide only structural integrity and stability to multimetallic enzymes to use their maximum efficiency but also directly participates in the functional properties of these bio-molecules. Zinc deficiency causes acrodermatitis enteropathica⁵, prostate cancer, diabetes, and brain diseases while its excess may cause serious neurological disorders such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases^{6,7}. It is contained in several alcohol dehydrogenase, aldolases, peptidases, phosphatases, transphosphorylase, phospholipase and is important in carbohydrate, lipid and protein metabolism. In the metallo-enzymes Zn^{II} is tetrahedrally coordinated with imidazole-N of histidyl residue, cystyl-S, pyridine-N, carboxylate-O of glutamate, aspartate and for water-O. For example in alcohol dehydrogenase two different orientation are abbreviated as ZnNS₂O (N = cys-46, 174, O = H₂O); carboxypeptidase is ZnN₂O₂ (N = His69, 169; O = H₂O); carbonic anhydrase is ZnN₃O (N = His93, 95, 117; O = H₂O). Zinc is recently using for recognizing base sequences in DNA. So called Zinc-fingure proteins contain 9 to 10 Zn²⁺ ions each of which coordinates to 4-amino acids.

Chemosensor

Sensor is a system that on stimulation by pressure, light, heat, magnetic, electric or any form of energy undergoes change of its structure reversibly⁸. "A chemical sensor is a device that transforms chemical information, ranging from the concentration of a specific sample component to total composition analysis, into an analytically useful signal. The chemical information, mentioned above, may originate from a chemical reaction of the analyte or from a physical property of the system investigated"⁹. Chemical sensors employ specific transduction techniques to give information about analyte. The most extensively used techniques employed in chemical sensors are optical absorption, luminescence, redox potential, refractive index and reflectivity¹⁰. Chemical sensors contain two basic functional units : a receptor unit and a transducer/reporter unit. Some sensors may include a spacer which is, for example, a membrane (Fig. 1). In the receptor part of a sensor the chemical information is transformed into a form of energy which may be measured by the reporter/transducer. The criteria for good sensors are (i) stability, (ii) ion selectivity, (iii) ion affinity, (iv) signal transduction, (v) fluorescent signaling, (vi) kinetically rapid sensitization, (vii) ease of delivery to target systems, and (viii) availability.

Fig. 1. Cartoon picture of designing receptor-reporter system for fluorescence sensing.

Among the various tools that transduce chemical information into observable parameters, fluorescence techniques are the most promising. Fluorescence techniques¹¹ have several advantages, including a large signal intensity, high sensitivity, ultrafast signal acquisition, submicrometer resolution, low probe concentration, and simple and cheap instrumentation. Taking advantage of these properties, research into the development of fluorescent labels and sensors has achieved remarkable success.

Zn-sensor

The concentration of free Zn^{2+} within biological cells varies from about 1 nM in the cytoplasm of many cells to about 1 mM in some vesicles. Because of large involvement of Zn^{2+} in biology the quantification of trace Zn^{2+} in these biological mechanisms has become more urgent.

Some structures of zinc sensors are given in Fig. 2. Herein, we have synthesized a, 6,6'-((1Z,1'Z)-(((ethane-1,2-diylbis(oxy))bis(2,1-phenylene))bis(azanylylidene))bis(methanylylidene))bis(3-methoxyphenol),

Fig. 2. Structures of some chemosensor sensing to Zn^{2+} in biological cytoplasm.

(H_2L), by the condensation of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzaldehyde (HMB) and 2,2'-(ethane-1,2-diylbis(oxy))dianiline (EDOD)¹². The ligand, H_2L serves as a fluorescent zinc sensor. The spectrophotometric titration of H_2L with Zn^{2+} at 25 °C in DMSO/water (HEPES buffer, pH = 7.4; v/v, 3/7) shows a gradual development of new bands on increasing the addition of Zn^{2+} in the range 0–50 μ m.

The absorption bands at 286 and 346 nm of H₂L have been decreased gradually and an intense broad new band appears at 400 nm along with a band at 316 nm. Upon addition of other biologically abundant metal ions such as Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, Co²⁺, Mn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ and other metal ions like Pb²⁺, Ba²⁺, Hg²⁺, Al³⁺ do not show any significant change of absorbance in the UV-Vis spectra of H₂L (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Absorbance spectra of H₂L upon addition of various metal ions in DMSO-buffer (HEPES, pH = 7.4) (v/v = 3/7) solution.

No significant change toward Cd^{2+} was observed even after addition of excess (~ 3 eqv.) of the above mentioned metal ions.

Upon addition of Zn^{2+} the bands of H_2L have been shifted to 316 and 400 nm respectively (Fig. 4). These observations suggest the undoubted conversion of free H_2L to the corresponding zinc complex. The red shifting of the bands upon complexation is attributed to an intramolecular charge transfer (ICT) through the chelation to Zn^{2+} forming ZnN_2O_4 distorted octahedral coordination with six-membered chelate ring via two nitrogen

Fig. 4. (A) Change in absorption spectra of H_2L ($50 \mu\text{M}$) upon addition of Zn^{2+} in DMSO/water (HEPES buffer, $\text{pH} = 7.4$, v/v, 3/7); (B) Non-linear plot of absorbance (at 400 nm) vs $[\text{Zn}^{2+}]$ for the corresponding UV-Visible titration. The DFT computed structure of $[\text{ZnL}]$.

donor centres of C=N and two oxygen donors of vanillinyl phenolates along with five member chelate rings from two oxygen donor centres of ether group (vide DFT computed structure in Fig. 4). The increase of conjugation reduces the energy gap between the HOMO-LUMO and causes red shifting. The DFT computation of optimized structures of H₂L and [ZnL] has calculated the ΔE (LUMO-HOMO) 3.73 eV and 3.47 eV, respectively (Fig. 5) which supports the spectral observation. It is suggested that the stoichiometry between H₂L and Zn²⁺ is 1 : 1, which is consistent with the results of the Job's plot (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5. Energy correlation of HOMO-LUMO gap between H₂L and [ZnL].

Fig. 6. The Job's plot shows 1 : 1 stoichiometry between [Zn²⁺] and [H₂L].

Fluorescence spectroscopic study

The fluorescence spectrum of H₂L with several cations (Na⁺, Al³⁺, Hg²⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺, Co²⁺, Mn²⁺, Fe³⁺, Pb²⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, Ba²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺) have been examined (Fig. 7) and the turn-on emission is observed in presence of Zn²⁺ at room temperature (25 °C). On increasing [Zn²⁺] to the solution of H₂L the fluorescence intensity increases at 472 nm and becomes saturated on adding ~1.1 equivalent of Zn²⁺ which results 835 fold fluorescence enhancement in THF/methanol (v/v, 3/7) and 767 fold enhancement in DMSO/water (v/v, 3/7) .

Fig. 7. Fluorescence ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 346 \text{ nm}$) responses of H₂L upon addition of various metal ions in DMSO/water (HEPES buffer, pH = 7.4; v/v, 3/7) at emission slit 7 nm.

The detection of Zn²⁺ by the fluorescent probe is very selective and has not been perturbed by biologically available metal ions like Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺; the Cd²⁺ shows a little perturbation while other interfering metal ions Co²⁺, Mn²⁺, Pb²⁺, Ni²⁺, Ba²⁺, Mg²⁺, Hg²⁺, Al³⁺ become almost innocent towards fluorescence intensity change (Fig. 9). This is observed even after addition of 5 equivalents of the above mentioned interfering metal ions.

The dramatic fluorescence enhancement response to the binding of H₂L to Zn²⁺ (using ZnCl₂ solution) may be ascribed to (i) the deprotonation of phenolic-OH and the cause of restriction of excited-state induced proton

Fig. 8. (A) Change in fluorescence intensity of H₂L upon addition of 50 μM Zn²⁺ at emission slit 8 nm; (B) Non-linear plot of fluorescence intensity (at 472 nm) vs [Zn²⁺] for the corresponding fluorescence titration.

Fig. 9. Fluorescence intensity changes profiles of 100 μM H₂L in DMSO/water (HEPES buffer, pH = 7.4; v/v, 3/7) in presence of selected metal ions. The excitation wavelength was 346 nm and the emission slit at 10 nm.

transfer (ESIPT)^{13,14}, (ii) the prohibition of intramolecular electron-transfer process and (iii) the chelation-enhancement of fluorescence process along with lowering of vibrational loss due to rigid molecular structure of the complex.

The limit of detection (LOD) of Zn^{2+} has been determined by 3 σ/m method and found to be as low as 0.018 μM . Fluorescent sensors are well established and powerful tools for analytical quantification of molecules and ions in high precision and high accuracy level.

Conclusion

Zinc is very useful in biology, industry and environment. Fluorescence spectroscopic technique is very sensitive, selective and is useful choice of estimation of biological ion concentration Zn^{2+} is recognized using vanillinyl Schiff base as fluorogenic chemosensor. The limit of detection is 0.018 μM and is the lowest in the series of aryl/heterocyclic fluorogenic Zn^{2+} sensor. Zinc induced turn-on fluorescence enhancement is observed at 472 which may specifically due to the cavity size of the chelate ring, structural rigidity on twisting of the donor backbone and the suppression of ESIPT.

Acknowledgements

Financial support from the West Bengal Department of Science & Technology, Kolkata, India (Sanction No. 228/1(10)/(Sanc.)/ST/P/S&T/9G-16/2012) and the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR, Sanction No. 01(2731)/13/EMR-III), New Delhi, India are gratefully acknowledged. One of us (CP) thanks University Grants Commission, New Delhi, India for Fellowship.

References

1. F. A. Cotton, G. Wilkinson, C. A. Murillo and M. Bochmann, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 6th ed., John Wiley, New York, 1999.
2. H. Sigel, "Metal Ions in Biological Systems : Zinc and its Role in Biology and Nutrition", CRC Press, 1993, Vol. 15.
3. I. Bertini, H. B. Gray, J. S. Valentine and J. Lippard, "Bioinorganic Chemistry", University Science Books, California, 1994.
4. D. W. Christianson and C. A. Fierke, *Accounts Chem. Res.*, 1996, **29**, 331.
5. S. Kury, B. Dreno, S. Bezieau, S. Giraudet, M. Kharfi, R. Kamoun and J.-P. Moisan, *Nat. Genet.*, 2002, **31**, 239.
6. M. P. Cuajungco and G. J. Lees, *Neurobiol. Dis.*, 1997, **4**, 137.
7. J.-Y. Koh, S. W. Suh, B. J. Gwag, Y. Y. He, C. Y. Hsu and D. W. Choi, *Science*, 1996, **272**, 1013.

7. J. J. R. F. da Silva and R. J. P. Williams, "The Biological Chemistry of Elements : The Inorganic Chemistry of Life", 2nd ed., Oxford UP, New York, 2001.
8. L. Prodi, *New J. Chem.*, 2005, **29**, 20.
9. A. Hulanicki, S. Geab and F. Ingman, *Pure & App. Chem.*, 1991, **63**, 1247; O. S. Wolfbeis, "Fibre Optic Chemical Sensors and Biosensors", CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1991, Vols. 1 and 2; G. Orellana and M. C. Moreno-Bondi, "Frontiers in Chemical Sensors : Novel Principles and Techniques", Springer, New York, 2005.
10. C. McDonagh, C. S. Burke and B. D. MacCraith, *Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **108**, 400.
11. B. Valeur, "Molecular Fluorescence : Principles and Applications", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, New York, 2002.
12. A. K. Bhanja, C. Patra, S. Mondal, D. Ojha, D. Chattopadhyay and C. Sinha, *RSC Adv.*, 2015, **5**, 48997.
13. J. E. Kwon, S. Lee, Y. You, K.-H. Baek, K. Ohkubo, J. Cho, S. Fukuzumi, I. Shin, S. Y. Park and W. Nam, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 8760.
14. D. Yang, Y. Yang and Y. Liu, *J. Clust. Sci.*, 2014, **25**, 467.